

CASE STUDY ON LANGUAGE DIFFICULTIES AND INTERVENTION FOR CHILDREN WITH AUTISM SPECTRUM DISORDER (ASD)

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ABSTRACT

Language development is crucial to a child's growth as it is a foundation for communication and social interaction. However, some children face challenges in developing their language skills due to different developmental disabilities, such as autism spectrum disorder (ASD). This study explores the language difficulties of children with ASD, utilizing a Descriptive Case Study to fully examine the experiences of the two subjects, Jake and Clark. It also involves the caretakers and therapists involved in the child's intervention process. This study is bounded by cognitive theory and behaviorism theory, offering an understanding of cognitive and behavioral aspects of language development in the context of ASD. The results reveal similarities and uniqueness in each case, as well as language difficulties and interventions experienced and received by both of the subjects. Also, the methodologies employed by the teachers and therapists working with the children emphasize practical and holistic intervention for continuous development. The implications of the findings highlight the importance of proactive and targeted interventions in promoting language development among children with ASD. This study contributes to a deeper comprehension of practical strategies and interventions supporting language growth in children with ASD.

Keywords: *autism spectrum disorder, psycholinguistics, language, cognitivist, behaviorist*

INTRODUCTION

The early years of a child's life, particularly between 0 and 8, are considered the golden age for language development. During this period, children's brains undergo significant growth, with 80% occurring by age 5. A child typically develops language proficiency, produces well-formed sentences, and acquires a substantial vocabulary (Sari et al., 2018). In addition, the family and the surrounding environment play a pivotal role in shaping a child's language skills through interactions that influence attitudes, speech styles, and vocabulary acquisition (Firmansyah, 2018). However, some children face obstacles in mastering language skills, and this is particularly evident in cases of autism spectrum disorder (ASD).

According to the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (the Fifth Edition) or DSM-5, ASD is a neurodevelopmental condition characterized by deficits in social interaction, communication challenges, and repetitive behaviors (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). Children with ASD often exhibit slow language development, involving receptive and expressive language disorders (Hashanah, 2018).

Understanding language development in children with ASD is essential, and the field of psycholinguistics can provide valuable insights about it. Psycholinguistics, the integration of psychology and linguistics, explores the cognitive processes underlying language use (Purba, 2018). It encompasses language production, perception, and acquisition, offering a comprehensive framework to study normal and disordered language phenomena (Suherman, 2015).

This present study is a case study on language difficulties and the interventions given to two male children who are diagnosed with ASD. This study shall provide an in-depth analysis of the type of disorder the subjects have, the difficulties they face regarding different linguistic skills, and the interventions they are undergoing. Utilizing a theoretical framework based on two major psychological theories in psycholinguistics, mainly Behaviorism by B. F. Skinner (1957) and Cognitivism by Jean Piaget (1952).

Generally, this study aimed to understand the case, the language difficulties, and the interventions for children with ASD. Specifically, it seeks to address the following aspects: (1) the case of the participants, (2) the

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language difficulties the participants have, (3) the interventions given to the participants, and (4) the methodologies used by teachers and therapists to work with the subjects.

METHODS

This study utilized a Descriptive Qualitative Study, specifically, a Descriptive Case Study. The instruments utilized in gathering the data are observation and interview. The researchers adopted an observation matrix called Autism Observation Checklist, developed by Turner (2015), and developed a semi-structured interview validated by language experts. Furthermore, the participants involved in the study are two male children named Jake and Clark, both of whom are diagnosed with ASD. Also, their caretakers, teachers, and therapists were involved in the study.

Moreover, the data-gathering procedure is conducted in three phases. Phase one involves the observation of the subjects, phase two involves an interview with the parents, and phase three involves the interview with the therapist and teacher of the children. The data analysis was also conducted in three phases. Phase one involves the printing of transcripts from the observation. Phase two involves organizing the data from the interviews gathered from the parents and therapist. Phase three involves coding the findings and putting them into themes using thematic analysis. Lastly, ethical guidelines were also observed during and after the process of data gathering and data analysis. Several ethical considerations were considered, which include Informed consent and voluntary participation, anonymity and confidentiality, data analysis and dissemination of the findings, and data protection.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Jake

Case Background of Jake

Several studies about ASD suggest that early signs often begin to emerge in the first two years of life. However, the specific signs can vary widely, and a formal diagnosis typically occurs around the age of 2 to 3. In the case of Jake, his caretaker stated that "Jake was officially diagnosed with ASD when we had him assessed in Manila at the age of four and a half." Globally, the mean age for ASD diagnosis ranges between 38 and 120 months (Daniels & Mandell, 2014).

Jake's caretaker took a proactive step in seeking assessment services that enabled them to find early symptoms and recognize Jake's specific needs. Jake's caretaker describes the early signs that were found in him. His caretaker stated, "He does not engage in conversation with us nor turn around when called. That was the time when Jake found it difficult to communicate and speak." One notable characteristic of ASD is communication challenges, and the difficulties mentioned by the caretaker align with the early signs of a person with ASD. Individuals with ASD often struggle with social interactions and communication. It is challenging for them to initiate or sustain conversations, make eye contact, or express themselves verbally.

In addition, Restricted, Repetitive, and Stereotyped Behaviors/Movements, which are a feature of ASD, were also observed in him. These behaviors include repetitive motor movements, routine adherence, intense interests, and sensory sensitivities (American Psychiatric Association, 2013). Jake's caretaker explained, "I noticed that Jake is now clapping his hands, tiptoeing, and sometimes he has what we call a 'reckless night' where he just cries incessantly. He does this from 1 am to 3 am". From the researchers' observation, Jake exhibits a narrow focus on his activities, an insistence on the sameness of routines, specifically that routines must be done in a particular order and limited repetitive motor mannerisms such as hand flapping and toe walking. Sensory sensitivities were also present to Jake. Jake's caretaker added, "Jake gets triggered when it's crowded, and his frustration builds up because he can't express what he wants. It's really in noisy environments that he gets frustrated". Kern et al. (2015) discuss how sensory challenges can contribute to emotional dysregulation in individuals with ASD. Difficulties in processing sensory information may lead to emotional distress, communication, and behavioral challenges.

Meanwhile, when asked about the cause of ASD or if Jake's family has a background of ASD, his caretaker narrated that "Jake was born prematurely at 32 weeks. He was not conceived in the usual way; he is an IVF baby who was inserted through a procedure, hence the 32-week gestation period." Several studies have shown that children who are born prematurely may face challenges in their development, and there is a correlation between premature birth and an increased risk of developmental issues. High rates of autism are found in preterm

populations, indicating that prematurity may present an increased likelihood of poor neurodevelopmental outcomes (Lavery et al. 2021). However, Lehti (2021) found out that IVF is not likely to increase the risk of ASDs. Jake's caretaker added, "At present, Jake is five years old, but his thinking and language abilities are at the level of a 3-year-old." Jake's development lags behind his current age. Bishop et al. (2017) explained that there is a connection between cognitive and language abilities wherein a delay in one aspect may impact the other. In Jake's case, his cognitive and language capacities both exhibit delays and show that ASD often involves complex interactions between various developmental aspects.

Language Difficulties

Expressive Language Difficulty

From our interview, Jake's caretaker enunciated that "Jake started talking when he was one until he was three years old. Then, when he turned four, his talking stage stopped... it was a challenge for him to talk when he was four and a half, just before turning five." Developmental delays in speech and language are not uncommon in children. Law et al. (2017) explained that various factors, including genetics, environmental influences, and neurological factors, can contribute to speech delays in early childhood. Children may sometimes experience temporary speech delays that can be solved with time and intervention. It is important to note that each child develops at their own pace, and some differences in language development are expected. However, continuous speech delays beyond a certain age may need further evaluation by professionals.

Additionally, Jake's caretaker stated, "When he wants something he cannot express, he throws tantrums. He resorts to hurting, like pinching; I end up with bruises. Now, what I do is I ask him what he wants. He then tells me 'I want' and points to the biscuit container, for example." The researchers found out that communication problems and tantrums are common in children with autism and that the lack of speech is a cause of these tantrums. The statement of Jake's caretaker shows that Jake experiences expressive language difficulties, particularly when he wants something and cannot communicate it verbally.

Meanwhile, based on the observation, the researchers discovered that he has difficulty holding conversations, has unusual language, and does not express pleasure, achievements, or interests with others. The researchers found out that it takes a minute for Jake to respond to his teacher. He uses terms in naming his teacher; for example, he uses the sound of the cat, "meow-meow," to refer to his teacher, whose name is Cath. Also, when expressing his wants, he points them out directly before uttering them.

Receptive Language Difficulty

As seen in Jake's case, his caretaker stated, "But he can understand the meaning because Jake can follow simple instructions." Compared to his expressive skills, his receptive skills are much better, wherein he can understand the basics of instructions given to him. The fact that Jake can follow simple instructions indicates that he has a foundational understanding of language, allowing him to interpret and act upon straightforward verbal commands.

Meanwhile, during observation, the researchers found out that Jake could understand his teacher's and therapist's instructions during his session. He can respond to his name, nod yes, or shake his head for no, and has good imitation skills. On the other hand, eye contact is still lacking with him when the researchers try to communicate with him.

Language Features Difficulty

When asked if Jake has trouble with specific aspects of language, like how words sound, how sentences are structured, or what words mean, his caretaker stated, "Jake indeed has challenges in communication. While he does not have issues with pronunciation, forming complete sentences poses a problem. He typically uses one or two words, but he understands the meanings, as he can follow simple instructions." Jake's case is described as having difficulty engaging in conversations and facing challenges in constructing sentences. Jake has relative strengths in certain language domains, such as pronunciation, but he has challenges in higher-order language functions, including sentence formation and pragmatic language use.

Echolalia

Jake has acquired Spanish and learned to recite the Spanish alphabet backward through watching Spanish videos on the internet. As his caretaker stated, "Jake primarily speaks English, but around age 4, almost 5, he learned to count in Spanish and Arabic. He went through the ABCs from Z to A in Spanish, backward... but the

doctor advised us to stop that.” Echolalia is a linguistic phenomenon where an individual repeats or echoes words, phrases, or entire sentences spoken by others. Mergl & Azoni (2015) found out that in ASD children with the predominant use of verbal communication, echolalia is a consistent phenomenon that is characterized as a language disorder, defined as the repetition of meaningless words just spoken by another person, occurring as a symptom of mental conditions.

Interventions

Consistent Routine

A consistent routine is recommended as part of therapeutic interventions for children with ASD. The consistency of routines can help individuals with ASD to navigate their environment more comfortably. In the case of Jake, his caretaker stated, “If he wants something, I only give it when he speaks, but if he doesn’t speak, he’ll just gesture to me, I won’t give it... I don’t want Jake to make it a routine that I just need to say a phrase to notice me... So now what I want his routine to be is that he imitates me, like in singing nursery rhymes, so that it helps him learn to communicate.” Rather than automatically fulfilling requests, the decision to respond only when Jake speaks, or gestures reflects a consistent approach to encouraging verbal or gestural communication as the primary means of expression. His caretaker also added, “Indeed, simple greetings like ‘good morning’ and ‘how are you’ matter. When you spend the whole day together, talking to him is crucial because he might lose those skills. I experienced it when I went on vacation for a week, leaving him with his grandparents. When I came back, he could not say simple greetings anymore.”

Occupational Therapy

The unique needs of individuals with ASD require a holistic and individualized approach to intervention. Jake has been working in an OT center for almost a year. Here, it was observed that he has improved with his overall development. As his caretaker stated, “There has been a significant improvement since we enrolled him in Special Learners. He now recognizes which uniform is for school and which is for the Center. He is excited because he started talking here. The teachers are incredibly kind, thoughtful, and caring. Jake prefers calm voices, and the teachers here provide that.” The statement of Jake’s caretaker highlights significant improvements in Jake’s behavior and communication since he underwent therapy. Jake’s ability to distinguish between uniforms for school and the Center demonstrates a cognitive and contextual understanding that reflects positive developmental progress. Jake’s excitement about talking and engagement in the learning environment positively indicates the program’s effectiveness.

Clark

Case Background of Clark

In the case of Clark, his caretaker states, “He was probably around three years old when he was diagnosed... it was at the age of 3 and a half when we noticed that he was not engaging in conversation with us.” Typically, at this age, children are expected to exhibit a significant vocabulary by this age and start forming simple sentences. The age of three is a crucial developmental stage for children’s language acquisition and social interaction.

Early signs that were observed in him as his caretaker narrated, “Calling his name, making eye contact – when we call his name, he does not turn around.” Typically, at the early age of a child, they should have demonstrated a behavior wherein they become attentive and aware when their name is called and can engage in eye contact during interactions. However, Clark’s case does not exhibit those behaviors.

In addition, sensory sensitivities, which are a feature of ASD, were also observed in him. Clark’s caretaker explained that “He does not like loud noises, and when his mom plays loud music, he dislikes it and turns it off.” Clark’s response to turning off loud music is a coping strategy to regulate his sensory input.

Meanwhile, when asked about the cause of his ASD, his caretaker stated that “He inherited autism from his father, and the varied environment contributed to his speech differences.” The caretaker emphasizes that Clark might have inherited autism from his father and associates environmental factors, specifically the different language exposure, as potential contributors to the development of ASD of Clark.

His caretaker added, “His abilities are not quite fitting for his age; although he is five years old, we still perceive him as a toddler, maybe around two years old.” Clark’s developmental stage is not consistent. According

to Ozonoff et al. (2014), there are uneven developmental profiles often observed in individuals with ASD. While some areas of development may be delayed, others may be relatively intact or even advanced, which may contribute to a situation where the child exhibits behaviors more typical of a younger age in specific aspects.

Language Difficulties

Expressive Language Difficulty

Expressive language difficulties are common in individuals with ASD. The challenges that may be present include limited vocabulary, difficulty forming sentences, or the use of unconventional means of communication (APA, 2013). Clark's caretaker stated, "When he cannot get what he wants, he resorts to hurting others, kicking in frustration." Clark has limited communication skills, including challenges in expressive language, and it contributes to his frustration and the use of alternative behaviors, such as aggression, to communicate needs. Meanwhile, during observation, the researchers found that he has difficulty holding conversations, uses unusual language, and does not express pleasure, achievements, or interests with others.

Receptive Language Difficulty

In our interview with Clark's caretaker, she stated, "When we speak, he imitates us... He also understands the meanings." Compared to his expressive skills, his receptive skills are much better. Clark has the ability to understand and comprehend simple meanings. Meanwhile, the researchers discovered that Clark could understand his teacher's instructions. He can respond when his name is called, can nod yes or shake his head for no, and has good imitation skills. His eye contact, as compared to Jake's, is more consistent when we try to communicate with him

Language Features Difficulty

When asked if Clark has trouble with specific aspects of language, like how words sound, how sentences are structured, or what words mean, his caretaker stated, "When we speak, he imitates us. The pronunciation is normal. He can form a sentence. Our names are recognized and known at home. He also understands meanings". Clark's tendency to imitate speech is a notable aspect of his language development. Clark's imitation could be a way for him to acquire language skills, and his ability to recognize and recall names may indicate a strength in memory and language-related skills. From the researchers' observations, although limited, Clark exhibits good pronunciation of words. As with his sentence construction, he can utter simple phrases when requesting and responding.

Echolalia

Echolalia can manifest in various ways, including immediate repetition of words or phrases heard from others, delayed repetition, and even phrases from movies or books (Thiemann-Bourque et al., 2018). "He switches languages, sometimes speaking in Mandarin. He learned it through the videos he watched." Clark's caretaker explained that he may have acquired Mandarin because of the videos he watched. Clark's ability to speak Mandarin reflects echolalia, which is commonly observed in individuals with ASD. Echolalia involves the repetition of words or phrases, often without apparent understanding of their meaning.

Interventions

Consistent Routine

Establishing a consistent routine is particularly crucial for children with ASD. Consistency provides predictability and a structured environment, which can be especially beneficial for individuals with ASD who often thrive on routine and may find unexpected changes challenging. In the case of Clark, his caretakers stated, "I teach him basic words like hello and good morning. When greeting each other with a 'good morning,' for example, we practice together. We engage in conversations when it is just the two of us to keep things interesting for him." Clark's caretaker's approach of teaching essential words like "hello" and "good morning" through imitation is a practical and effective strategy in encouraging language development. Imitation is a foundational skill in early language acquisition. Imitation is a critical mechanism for children to learn and practice new words, helping build their vocabulary.

Occupational Therapy

Clark has been working in an OT center. Here, it was observed that he has improved in his overall development. The caregiver's observations show Jake's positive attitude toward therapy and attribute his improvement to the Center's interventions. As his caretaker stated, "He likes saying 'let us go therapy' now. Being at the Center has been a tremendous help, and he has shown improvement here." Clark expresses enthusiasm for his therapy sessions, which shows a positive attitude toward therapeutic interventions. This positive association is crucial in promoting active participation and engagement in therapeutic activities.

Methodologies Employed by the Therapists

Occupational Therapy

Both subjects are currently undergoing an occupational therapy session at SLTC. Both are under the care of different professionals in the Center, such as SPED teachers, Psychologists, Physical therapists, and Occupational therapists. In the study of Herbert et al. (2014), their research participants, including an occupational therapist and speech pathologist who works multidisciplinary, agreed that occupational therapy plays an "indispensable" role when children with ASD do not yet communicate or communicate with difficulty. Here, we interviewed three therapists working with the subjects. During our interview session, there are three approaches teachers and therapists employ: the holistic approach, the practical approach, and the play-based teaching, all of which are under occupational therapy.

Holistic Approach

Being holistic is often used in a center where occupational therapy is the focus. A holistic approach considers various aspects of a child's development, including its social, emotional, physical, and mental dimensions. This approach recognizes that a child's well-being is interconnected with each other and that addressing multiple aspects of a child's individuality is essential for its progress. "Here, in the Center, we utilize assessment software...we will see there what the needs of the child are if it is aligned with his age range. This is where we assess and identify the strengths and weaknesses, determining the areas that need improvement." Gee et al. (2018) have said that occupational therapy is a holistic method. The occupational therapy process is designed to be holistic in nature, capturing the client as the individual, their family, and other supports while at the same time taking into consideration the individual's interaction with the physical, social, and attitudinal contexts of function.

Practical Approach

Teachers and Therapists in the Center initiate practical strategies within their sessions to improve the well-being of autistic children. Under a practical approach, they focus on language prerequisites such as Attention, Listening, Turn-taking, and Imitation skills of the children. "We target language prerequisite, as we learned from webinars and speech pathologists, is building the child's attention. Here at the Center, our activities focus on enhancing eye and hand coordination, addressing the foundational skills needed before a child can effectively communicate." Teacher 1 answered when asked about the approach they used. Teacher 1 also added, "The second one is the child's listening skills. If they've developed the ability to listen...it also helps the attention skills of the children." Teacher 1 describes that the focus on listening skills is through auditory intervention, which they employ through action songs and imitation. Teacher 1 also added, "Then, of course, developing turn-taking skills involves engaging with other kids. It's difficult to foster turn-taking skills without the involvement of other children." Teacher 1 emphasizes that in involving other kids with their activities, the child develops the social context of language use. Teacher 1 also added that "then imitation skills, we target that through activities focusing on gross motor skills, action songs, and other forms of imitation activities involving movements and actions." Teacher 1 suggests that imitation is critical for children with ASD because it is a tool for both learning and socialization for them.

Play-Based Learning

When asked about the other approach they employ when working with the subjects, Teacher 1 added, "We teach children through play. We believe that through play, children learn more effectively, and we've found in our teaching journey at SLTC that playing is a powerful way for children to learn." They discovered that playing is where the subjects learn to engage, which will later develop their language and communication skills. Meanwhile, Therapist 1 added, "We have kids who entered here with ASD, and some of them don't know how to play. When

you give them toys, they show no interest. They want to run around. So, the first thing we teach them is how to play and interact with toys.” The statement shows that the play behavior of Autistic children is different from that of children with typical development. Typically, at their age, they should have known how to use toys for play and interaction. Children are inherently social and engage with others. But kids with autism are not as social, and they need to be brought into that social world through play.

Strategies for Communication Skills

Therapist 1 stated, “So, the strategies we implement here, especially for their social and communication skills, it doesn’t necessarily involve direct conversation. Instead, we teach them how to interact and play with other children.” The strategy they use is activities involving pairs of students and teachers. These activities serve as a structured way for them to practice and reinforce social skills. Children learn the importance of cooperation and engagement in a social context through turn-taking and sharing of toys.

Teacher 1 also stresses that “when a child hasn’t started speaking yet, we initially teach them essential words. For example, words related to body parts can be used to express if something hurts when they communicate.” They introduce words that have immediate relevance to the child’s daily life. Functional words, such as body parts and words related to everyday living, are being taught. Their strategy is teaching words associated with the child’s immediate needs and experiences to enhance their communication ability.

Individualize Education Plan (IEP)

The use of IEP serves as a basis for the teachers and therapists regarding what activities they will give to the subjects. It is one universal tool available to schools or Centers for individuals with special needs to record and track goals and objectives that are individualized and responsive to students’ needs. In our interview, teacher #1 states, “We still base our approach on the Individualized Education Program (IEP) because the IEP is tailored to each student, considering their age range. Every student has their own IEP, and that’s where we gather all the activities, we need to do with them and the skills that need improvement based on our assessments.” Teachers and therapists provide a flexible approach for each individual they are handling. It emphasizes a student-centered approach. IEPs are tailored to each own needs. As children with ASD have different cases, they also have different needs and ways to give intervention about it.

When asked if there is an activity related to language, Therapist 1 stated, “It has a specific section in the IEP dedicated to language skills, encompassing receptive and expressive skills. For example, the receptive language aspect is linked to both gross motor and fine motor skills, especially in tasks like following directions and instructions.” In their IEPs, language skills are integrated into gross and fine motor skills activities. This integration showcases that a child’s language development needs multiple activities.

In their activities, Teacher 2 added, “We prioritize improving their bigger muscles before addressing the smaller muscles, particularly those used in oral activities like speech.” Better muscle coordination contributes to better speech production. Teacher 2 also added, “We start with their big muscles because it’s challenging to teach a child to say ‘dog’ or ‘cat’ if their big muscles aren’t developed enough. For instance, if they can’t clap their hands or wipe their nose, we address those before moving on to activities like saying ‘la’ or ‘ba.’”

Teacher 2 added, “They need to be given activities that involve crossing the midline. While we might initially think that a child with a language disorder or difficulty has a problem in the oral area, it’s related to the brain. That’s why left and right coordination is essential, where both the left and right brain of the child are engaged.” These kinds of activities can strengthen the body and brain through coordination and muscle strength, contributing to speech production.

Collaborative Teaching

Teachers and therapists from the Center collaborate with other professionals to better execute therapy services. Specifically, they collaborate with the children’s SPED teacher, parents, and speech therapist. As Teacher 2 stated, “Some of the kids here have SPED teachers who attend meetings with us. They share observations about what needs improvement for the child and what they notice in school or the classroom.” This collaborative effort provides a more comprehensive understanding of the child’s needs and areas for improvement. Regular communication and meetings between SPED teachers and therapists contribute to a unified approach to the child’s development, aligning school and center strategies.

Therapist 2 added, “Here in the province, finding speech therapists is challenging. Most of our transactions and communication with speech therapists are done through Messenger.” The teachers working with

the children narrated that there are a lot of parents looking for speech therapy services from them. Since it is an occupational therapy center, what they do is assess the children first and report it to a speech therapist outside the region through online platforms. Then, the speech therapist will suggest that the child undergo sessions in occupational therapy. If improvements in language abilities are seen, then the child will undergo sessions in occupational therapy.

Aside from that, parents are also involved in the child's therapy. Teacher 2 added, "Their role is very crucial... We invite them to almost every activity during sessions inside the classroom. This is to observe how we handle teaching." By allowing parents to observe teaching methods firsthand, the teachers help parents understand why specific techniques are effective in the classroom and encourage them to implement similar approaches at home.

Lastly, teacher 2 added, "During every session, we create a daily note, which serves as our writeup with observations, activities, and interventions. We also provide feedback after each session." Their daily notes serve as a record of the child's activities, interventions, and progress during sessions. The feedback session, including post-session discussions, helps maintain transparency and ensures that all parents or caretakers are informed about the child's development. It also allows timely intervention adjustments based on the child's responses and needs.

Reward System

Technological tools were also utilized by the therapist and teacher to deal with the daily activities of the children. Teacher 2 stated, "There's the text exchange communication system. It is a tool to address the misconception that non-verbal children aren't listening... Sometimes, it becomes a reward; before they watch or play, we can work on improving their requesting skills by having them say or ask for what they want, like saying, 'I want to watch.'" The provided statements align with the behaviorist theory, which involves associating an involuntary response with a stimulus, eventually causing the individual to respond to the stimulus in a particular way. In this case, gadgets serve as conditioned stimuli. Gadgets become associated with learning and positive reinforcement—rewards, such as allowing the child to watch or play, act as unconditioned stimuli. By pairing rewards with specific behaviors or requests, the child associates the desired actions with positive outcomes.

CONCLUSION

Based on the gathered data, the following conclusions were drawn: It was observed that while children with ASD have the same diagnosis, the individual cases within this spectrum exhibit significant similarities and differences. This implies that ASD is not the same entity; rather, it encompasses a wide range of characteristics and challenges unique to each child. In the case of the subjects, both exhibit behavioral and sensory sensitivities. They differ when it comes to the cause of ASD. It is also noted that their development lags behind the development of typical children.

In terms of language, both exhibit strong receptive skills as compared to their expressive skills. Both subjects have strengths and weaknesses in terms of language features. Both subjects developed echolalia, showcasing positive imitation and expressive skills. On the other hand, a negative aspect is the lack of functional meaning associated with their utterance. Practical interventions such as building a consistent routine with the child and ensuring consistent attendance to therapy sessions have shown positive results in their abilities. Provide a development for their development.

Moreover, through the results of interviews with teachers and therapists, the data highlighted the role of occupational therapy in contributing to language development. Specifically, improving language prerequisite and motor skills through practical, holistic, and play-based interventions. This approach to therapy recognizes the interconnectedness of motor skills and language development, emphasizing that interventions addressing both aspects can provide positive outcomes. Other factors, such as the use of IEPs, developing strategies for communication, collaborative teaching, and using reward systems, contribute to the progress of children with ASD.

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